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Effect of Compensation Management on Workers Satisfaction in Nkwen Baptist Hospital Northwest Region of Cameroon

KEYWORDS

compensation,
management,
satisfaction

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The relevance of studying the factors influencing employee satisfaction in a medical organization is driven by the necessity to improve motivation, work quality, and patient care levels, as well as to reduce staff turnover and ensure stability in the healthcare sector.

The aim of the study was to investigate the effects of compensation management on workers satisfaction in Nkwen Baptist Hospital Bamenda. The area of study was Nkwen Baptist Health Centre of the North West Region of Cameroon.

Methodology. The study adopted causal research design. The study made use of survey data collected with the help of a structured questionnaire through random sampling and analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics.

Results. Results from the ordinary least square revealed that direct financial compensation, indirect financial compensation, and non-financial compensation has a positive impact on workers' satisfaction.

Recommendation. It was recommended that the management of Nkwen Baptist Hospital should ensure that the direct financial compensation provided to workers is competitive within the health care industry; evaluate the company's benefits package to ensure it is comprehensive and meets the needs of the workforce; gather feedback from employees to understand their preferences and tailor the non-financial compensation offerings accordingly.

Conclusion. The findings suggest that fair and competitive compensation packages, transparency, and performance-based incentives are essential for enhancing employee motivation-and job satisfaction, reduce turnover rates, and attract top talent.

Novelty. The findings contribute to the existing body of knowledge on compensation management and employee satisfaction in the healthcare sector, Nkwen Baptist Hospital in Cameroon, a context that has received limited attention in previous research.

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INTRODUCTION

The relevance of studying the factors affecting employee satisfaction in a medical organization is determined by the need to improve the quality of provided services, reduce staff turnover, and create favorable working conditions. Understanding the key determinants of satisfaction allows for the development of effective human resource management strategies, which in turn promote increased motivation and professional commitment among staff. In the current context of healthcare system reforms and growing competition among medical organizations, investigating these factors has become critically important for ensuring sustainability and enhancing the efficiency of medical institutions.

Nkwen Baptist hospital Bamenda is an important healthcare facility in Cameroon, providing essential medical services to the local community. Understanding the effect of compensation management on worker satisfaction is essential for improving employee morale, reducing turnover rates and enhancing patient care.

The health care sector faces significant challenges in maintaining worker satisfaction, specifically in compensation management fair compensation is crucial for employee motivation, job satisfaction, and overall performance. However, many healthcare institutions struggle to provide competitive compensation packages leading to dissatisfaction and turnover among skilled professionals. This problem statement highlights the challenges healthcare institutions face in managing compensation, which can impact employee satisfaction, motivation, and performance.

By examining the effect of compensation management on worker satisfaction in Nkwen Baptist Hospital Bamenda, this study aims to provide insights into the complex relationship between compensation and employee satisfaction in the healthcare sector. Specifically, the study sought to:

- Ascertain the effect of direct financial compensation on workers satisfaction in the NBH Bamenda

- Analyse the effect of indirect financial compensation on workers satisfaction in the NBH Bamenda

- Explore the effect of non-financial compensation on workers satisfaction in the NBH Bamenda

Research Hypotheses

H0: Direct financial compensation has no significant effect on workers satisfaction in the NBH Bamenda

H0: Indirect financial compensation has an insignificant influence on worker's satisfaction in the NBH Bamenda

H0: There is no substantial effect of non-financial compensation on workers satisfaction in the NBH Bamenda

LITERATURE REVIEW

Resources Review

Factors influencing job satisfaction among healthcare professionals include working conditions, salary level and social benefits, the attitude of colleagues and management, workload, opportunities for professional growth, recognition of merits, etc.

According to K. Karjalainen et al., key themes of organizational attractiveness in healthcare are aspects of patient and healthcare worker well-being, opportunities for professional development, and organizational responsibilities [1].

N. S. Sarkhadov et al. point out that more than half of the surveyed medical professionals of various specialties chose the medical profession out of a desire to help people, which underscores the altruistic nature of medical practice. Despite high workloads, economic instability, and a lack of respect for the profession, a significant proportion of the surveyed medical professionals' express satisfaction with their work, indicating intrinsic motivation and a commitment to continuous self-improvement [2].

P. Cantarelli et al. identify a set of factors associated with increased job satisfaction among healthcare professionals, depending on the department, organization, and regional management. The authors study factors affecting job satisfaction among more than 70 thousand employees of Italian regional health authorities. According to the researchers, environmental characteristics, organizational management methods, and team coordination mechanisms correlate with professional satisfaction [3].

A. B. Timurzieva examines issues of patient satisfaction, as well as satisfaction among medical and non-medical staff of healthcare organizations, key motivating and demotivating factors in the professional activities of medical workers, and models of

relationships between healthcare professionals and patients. The researcher analyzes some of the most important criteria for the satisfaction of patients, medical, and non-medical staff of a medical organization in the course of healthcare delivery [4].

W. Pomaranik and M. Kludacz-Alessandri examined the influence of demographic, organizational, and behavioral factors on medical staff satisfaction, such as social competencies, staff mobility, patient orientation, gender, and education level. According to the researchers, among the factors exerting a positive but lesser influence on job satisfaction were staff mobility and education level. The influence of gender, patient orientation, and social competence had the least pronounced, yet most significant, impact on job satisfaction [5].

N. Fadaie et al. examined the impact of three variables – knowledge management (KM), job satisfaction (JS), and organizational effectiveness (OE) – on employees of a network of medical and treatment institutions. According to the researchers, knowledge management processes positively influenced performance and job satisfaction. However, no significant correlation was found between knowledge transfer and job satisfaction among employees of the healthcare and treatment network [6].

A. Radlović and T. Safiye investigated the relationship between motivation and job satisfaction, as well as assessing factors predicting job satisfaction among healthcare workers. Their results showed that extrinsic motivation is a significant positive predictor of job satisfaction [7].

A. Gkliati and A. Saiti found that the most important factors for job satisfaction of medical professionals are the nature of their work and a high level of autonomy, as well as the level of commitment of medical professionals, which is sustained by enhancing their positive emotions and sense of professional well-being [8].

G. Jain et al. identified a statistically significant positive relationship between human resource management practices and overall job satisfaction. The work environment and performance appraisal were the most significant factors determining job satisfaction [9].

R. Cunningham et al. study factors (intrinsic rewards, workplace relationships, extrinsic rewards, and work-life balance) influencing job satisfaction among healthcare professionals. According to the researchers, overall job satisfaction was highest among healthcare executives and general practitioners and lowest among environmental health specialists and nurses [10].

J. Svanström et al. write that an expanded scope of practice, leadership and management effectiveness, and work-related stress significantly influence their job satisfaction. According to the researchers, an expanded span of control negatively affected job satisfaction. Factors related to work stress, particularly high demands and strained relationships, were negatively associated with job satisfaction, while control and support positively contributed to increased job satisfaction [11].

C. Kuzey examines key aspects of job satisfaction among knowledge workers in healthcare. Using factor analysis, the researchers identified six variables: managerial attitude, organizational support, job security, compensation and pay, working conditions, and colleague attitudes [12].

A. Nurmeksela et al. identified multiple interconnections between activities of nurse managers, job satisfaction of nurses, patient satisfaction, and medication errors. The study results indicate that nurse managers should focus on improving nursing practice by organizing work of nurses in a way that makes staff feel supported, motivated, and secure [13].

Y. Wang and Y. B. Tang investigated the influence of organizational support and professional identity on job satisfaction among Chinese medical social workers. According to the authors, organizational support and professional identity significantly impact job satisfaction [14].

M. Top and O. Gider identified a significant and positive correlation between job satisfaction and organizational commitment [15].

T. Verulava et al. identified factors influencing the job satisfaction of primary healthcare organization employees: individual characteristics, financial and non-financial incentives, organizational structures and processes, including supervision, leadership, fairness and accountability for resource allocation, staff dynamics and team cohesion, relationships with colleagues and management, relationships with patients, intellectual stimulation, and opportunities for continuing medical education [16].

The results of H. V. Osei et al. show that career satisfaction negatively affects the turnover intention of healthcare workers. A high level of burnout exacerbates the negative relationship between career satisfaction and the intention to quit [17].

N. J. Yanchus et al. found that civility, procedural justice, and autonomy influenced job satisfaction, which in turn predicted turnover intention. Psychological safety directly predicted turnover intention [18].

A. M. Mosadeghrad studies the impact of a Strategic Collaborative Quality Management (SCQM) program on the job satisfaction of hospital staff. After implementing the program, the hospital reported significant improvement in several aspects of job satisfaction, such as management and supervision, organizational policies, task demands, and working conditions [19].

Z. Chen et al. propose humane management principles to enhance job satisfaction of medical staff, further strengthen the scientific and standardized management of the hospital, improve the quality of medical services, and increase the comprehensive potential of the hospital [20].

Q. Chen et al. study job satisfaction and its influencing factors among young healthcare workers in a public general hospital. The researchers suggest that to meet the needs of young medical staff and improve their satisfaction, hospitals can consider optimizing working conditions, increasing compensation, improving internal communication, shaping hospital culture, and managing employee careers [21].

N. Li et al. believe that a complaint-free performance management system increases the internal satisfaction of medical records department staff, including satisfaction with the work itself, career development, and recognition. It enhances external satisfaction regarding aspects such as salary and social security, management policies, and interpersonal relationships [22].

M. D. Gornostalev et al. developed a questionnaire designed to assess the satisfaction of medical workers. The researchers describe the architecture of their proprietary questionnaire, which provides for satisfaction assessment based on four infrastructural indicators (comfort of stay, external appearance of medical organizations, technical equipment, digitalization and artificial intelligence), as well as the use of metrics: the Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI) and the Employee Net Promoter Score (eNPS) [23].

Therefore, the research shows that organizational attractiveness in healthcare is determined by the well-being of patients and medical staff, opportunities for professional growth, and organizational responsibilities. Job satisfaction depends on environmental factors, management, colleagues, the nature of the work, working conditions, etc. Intrinsic and extrinsic rewards, knowledge management, and psychological safety also influence satisfaction and desire of employees to remain in the profession, reducing burnout and staff turnover. Furthermore, studies indicate the necessity of focusing on optimizing working conditions, increasing compensation, improving internal communication, developing corporate culture, and managing employee careers.

Conceptual Review

Compensation Management

Compensation management is an essential component of the human resources management approach to organizational productivity. It is concerned with the design, implementation, and management of general compensation systems aimed at improving the performance of companies, teams, and individuals (Yadav and Aspal [24]). According to Milkovich and Newman, remuneration is an important tool for attracting and retaining bright individuals who are committed to their roles within the firm. It refers to the procedure through which employees are compensated for their contributions at work [25]. Ardana advanced that compensation is everything received by employees as a reward for its contribution to company or organization. Compensation is everything that employees receive as a reward for their work [26].

Financial compensation

Financial compensation can be divided by direct and indirect compensation. Then indirect compensation consists of the benefit program, i. e., health insurance, life insurance, pensions and labour insurance, payments outside working hours as holiday programs, annual leave and maternity leave, vehicles, office space and parking lots. According to Dessler, direct financial payments take the form of wages, salaries, incentives or benefits, commissions and bonuses [27]. Mondy tells that financial compensation consist of direct financial compensation and indirect financial compensation [28].

Direct financial compensation

According to Nawawi, direct compensation is a reward better known as salary or wages paid permanently to an employee based on a fixed period of time [29]. To add, Wibowo stated that it is a management compensation, such as wages and salaries or pay for performance, such as incentives and gain sharing [30]. Moreover, it is described from Dessler that usually the direct compensation is limited to direct cash as obtained by employees on a weekly, monthly, bi-monthly, or yearly basis from their rendering performance as the particular organization staff

Indirect financial compensation

Indirect compensation consists of the benefit program that is; health insurance, life insurance, pensions and labour insurance, payments outside working hours as holiday programs, annual leave and maternity leave, vehicles, office space and parking lots. Another study by Milkovich, Gerhart, and Hannon focused on the role

of fringe benefits in attracting and retaining employees. The researchers found that organizations that offered a wide range of fringe benefits experienced higher employee loyalty and reduced turnover rates [31]. Indirect compensation, as termed by Dessler, is the non-financial or indirect financial payments received by the employees as a means to continue their employment with the firm.

Non-financial Compensation

Nonfinancial Compensation on the other hand can be divided into occupations with interesting tasks, challenges, responsibilities, recognition and sense of accomplishment and; the working environment, as sound policies, competent supervisors, happy working atmosphere and a comfortable working environment. Grant indicated that intrinsic rewards, such as recognition and opportunities for growth, had a significant positive effect on employee engagement and job performance [32].

Worker's satisfaction

Worker satisfaction in this study connotes job satisfaction. Luthans says "job satisfaction is a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experience". Luthans explained that the factors that influence job satisfaction are the work itself, salary, opportunity of promotion, observation, team work, and friends [33]. According to Robbins and Timothy, there are five factors that make a person satisfied with his or her job [34]. These factors are mentally challenging work, equitable rewards, supportive working conditions, supportive colleagues, and personality-job fit. Mathis and Jackson [35] append "job satisfaction is a positive emotional state resulting from one's job experience". The dimension of job satisfaction is the work itself, salary, confession, supervision, good cooperation with friends, and also opportunity to expand.

Figure 1 Conceptual framework of the effect of compensation management on workers satisfaction

This framework considers three major effect compensation management has on workers satisfaction in the light of direct financial compensation, Indirect financial compensation, and non-financial compensation

Theoretical Review

Equity theory [36]

Considered one of the justice theories, equity theory was first developed in the 1960s by Stacy Adams, a workplace and behavioural psychologist, who asserted that employees seek to maintain equity between the inputs that they bring to a job and the outcomes that they receive from it against the perceived inputs and outcomes of others [Ibid]. According to Decenzo and Robbins [37], Stacey Adam's Equity theory focuses on determining whether the distribution of resources is fair to both relational partners.

The implications of the Equity theory are that, the manager should be equitable in managing personnel in order to guarantee motivation; fairness and personnel retention. This taking into consideration the fact that, employees determine what their equitable return should be after comparing their inputs and outcomes with those of her co-workers. This concept is referred to as "social comparison". If employees perceive that their inputs and outcomes are equitable compared to others, they are more likely to experience job satisfaction. On the other hand, if they perceive inequity, it can lead to feelings of dissatisfaction.

Theory of Negotiated Wages [38]

The theory of negotiated wages, also known as the collective bargaining theory of wages, suggests that wages are determined through a process of negotiation between employers and employees (usually represented by labour unions). According to Dunlop, wages are not solely determined by supply and demand forces in the labour market but are influenced by the bargaining power of both parties.

The theory of negotiated wages implies that the outcome of wage negotiations depends on the relative bargaining power of employers and employees. If workers have strong bargaining power, they are more likely to secure higher wages and better working conditions. Conversely, if employers have greater bargaining power, they may be able to keep wages low. This relates with the study in that the theory highlights the importance of collective bargaining and labour unions in shaping wage outcomes, as well as the role of non-market factors in wage determination.

Wage Fund Theory [39]

According to the theory, wages depend on the relative amount of capital available for the payment of workers and the size of the labour force. The wage fund theory assumes that the size of the wage fund is fixed in the short run and that wages are determined by dividing the fund among the available workers. Therefore, an increase in the number of workers would lead to a decrease in wages, while a decrease in the number of workers would result in higher wages. This theory has been criticized for its oversimplification of wage determination, as it does not consider factors such as worker productivity, skills, or demand-side factors. It also assumes a fixed wage fund, which may not hold true in reality.

Empirical Review

Roshan examined the effect of financial and non-financial compensation towards Employee Job Satisfaction [40]. To produce numeric analysis and testing hypothesis, the researchers used ANOVA Test to measure education level, job position and, working departments with employees' job satisfaction. The Ordinary Least Square (OLS) Method was used to measure the effect of financial and non-financial compensation towards employees' job satisfaction. The analysis was performed through SPSS 26. The testing included 150 respondents of assistant, officer and, managerial level from administration, operation and, credit departments of commercial banks from Maharajung to Balaju Ringroad Kathmandu. The main research findings revealed that financial and non- financial compensation had a significant effect on employee job satisfaction. The finding also showed that the job satisfaction significantly depends on their current education, job position and, working department too. Similarly, the impact of financial compensation towards job satisfaction was higher than that of non-financial compensation in employees' job satisfaction. The financial and non-financial compensation had positive impact on employees' job satisfaction.

Chizoba investigated the impact of indirect financial compensation on job satisfaction in private universities in North Central Nigeria. The paper adopted a singular source of data collection. The secondary source of data generation, the data was analyzed using the content analysis approach. This is because of its major dependence on the secondary source data. The study established that competitive salary and indirect compensation had a positive and significant influence on employees' job satisfaction. The study concludes that incentive plans motivate

workers for higher efficiency and productivity. It can improve the workflow and work methods; indirect compensation is a non-monetary benefit offered and provided to employees instead of the services provided by them to the organization and employees become more engaged when their performance is properly recognized by their employer. The study recommends that the universities administration can influence Employee performance by communicating to the employees that they value their contribution and also encouraging employee participation in the decision-making process of the compensation system at the universities. When employees feel that their opinions are valued at the organizations they work for, they tend to exhibit loyalty and commitment due to the sense of belongingness and trust from the management.

Research Gap

Most studies on compensation management and employee satisfaction have been conducted in specific industries or regions, leaving a gap in understanding the dynamics in the healthcare sector of northwest Region, Cameroon, particularly in the Nkwen Baptist Hospital Bamenda.

METHODS

Research design

The research design that has been employed in this study is the causal research design. This is a type of conclusive research design which attempts to establish a cause-and-effect relationship between two or more variables.

Data collection

In this study, primary data was used since information needed for analysis was best gotten through a structured questionnaire properly designed with indicators to capture the variables of the study.

The main instrument used to collect data for the study was a structured questionnaire. The population of the study constituted the 520 employees of the NBH Bamenda. The simple random sampling technique has been employed in this study. The sample size for the study was determined using Taro Yameni's Formula (TYF) as stated below:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

where, n= the sample size

N = the finite population

e = level of significance or tolerable error (5% or 0.05)

1= unity or constant

When N = 520 personnel, then

$$n = \frac{520}{1 + 520(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{520}{1 + 520(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{520}{1 + 520(0.0025)}$$

$$n = 226$$

Model specification

The regression coefficient models was used to determine the extent to which the dependent variables impact on the independent variable. The independent variable is Compensation management with the following dimensions: direct financial compensation; indirect financial compensation; non-financial compensation. The dependent variable is worker's satisfaction

Worker's satisfaction = f (Compensation management)

Compensation management = (DFC, IFC, NFC)

WS = $\beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{DFC} + \beta_2 \text{IFC} + \beta_3 \text{NFC} + \beta_3 \text{longe} + \beta_3 \text{DP} + \mu$, where:

WS: Worker's satisfaction,

DFC: Direct financial compensation,

IFC: Indirect financial compensation,

NFC: Non-financial compensation,

Longe: Longevity in Service

DP: Post of responsibility

β_0 is the intercept,

β_1 , β_2 , and β_3 , are the coefficient of change, and

μ is the error term.

Estimation technique

The ordinary least squares techniques was used to estimate the parameters.

Validity and Reliability instruments

The validity of the instrument was evaluated for face and content validity. To assess the reliability or consistency of our test items, we used the Cronbach's alpha. The Cronbach's alpha is used as the coefficient to measure data reliability level.

RESULTS

Reliability Test

The study conducted a pilot study to verify the precision of the research tools used to measure the independent and dependent variables. Cronbach's alpha was calculated for the explanatory variables, and the results are summarised in the table below. Also the result of the dependent variables which happens to be workers' satisfaction was also presented in the same table.

Table 1

Cronbach Alpha Coefficient table for both dependent
and independent variables

Variables	Number of items	Cronbach Alpha
Direct Financial Compensation	8	0.9177
Indirect Financial Compensation	8	0.8590
Non-Financial Compensation	7	0.8934
Workers' satisfaction	7	0.9275

Source: Field Survey, May 2025

The results in table1: show the reliability of four different scales or dimensions based on their Cronbach's alpha coefficient values. Cronbach's alpha is a measure of the scaling of constructs, which means it indicates how well the items within each dimension or scale are measuring the same underlying construct. A higher Cronbach's alpha value indicates better scale and reliability.

The results suggest that the scales or dimensions are reliable measures for their intended constructs, and can be used with confidence in this research or practical applications. Generally speaking, a Cronbach's alpha of 0.7 or above is appropriate. While some writers claim that Cronbach's alpha values of 0.70 or above signify satisfactory dependability, others contend that this cutoff point is too low and claim that values of 0.80 or even 0.90 are necessary for high levels of internal consistency. Cronbach's alpha George and Mallery [41] advise a cutoff of 0.70, although they emphasise that this is only a rule of thumb and that the appropriate number will vary depending on the measure's intended application and the context in which it is employed. Cronbach's alpha should have a minimum value of 0.70, according to Nunnally and Bernstein [42], while values of 0.80 or above are preferred for research-related metrics. Cronbach's alpha values between 0.70 and 0.90 are typically considered adequate for research purposes, according to DeVellis, while the precise cutoff depends on the measurement context and goal. According to Streiner [43], values of 0.70 to 0.80 for Cronbach's alpha are at the very least adequate for research purposes; however, values of 0.80 or higher are recommended. It is important to remember that these recommended criteria are not generally accepted, and studies should carefully analyse the particular context and goal of their measurement when deciding what constitutes an acceptable value of Cronbach's alpha.

Table 2

Summary of Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
nor_ws	184	.6628239	.3714469	0	1
nor_dfc	185	.4076859	.263089	0	1
nor_ifc	185	.4020692	.2684349	0	1
nor_nfc	185	.5884322	.3585029	0	1
longe	185	2.162162	1.186736	1	5
dutypost	185	1.524324	.5007632	1	2

Source: Field Survey, May 2025

Workers' satisfaction, reflected by a mean of 0.6628 and a standard deviation of 0.3714, indicates a generally positive sentiment among employees, with scores ranging from 0 to 1. This suggests that most employees express a significant degree of satisfaction, although there is notable variability in individual perceptions.

Direct Financial Compensation shows a lower mean of 0.4077 with a standard deviation of 0.2631, revealing a less uniform satisfaction level in this area compared to overall job satisfaction. The range of scores from 0 to 1 indicates that while some employees are content with their direct compensation, others may have more critical views.

Similarly, Indirect Financial Compensation has a mean of 0.4021 and a standard deviation of 0.2684, indicating a somewhat similar level of satisfaction variability as direct compensation. This suggests that employees' perceptions of indirect benefits, such as insurance or healthcare programs, are also diverse across the workforce.

Non-Financial Compensation, with a higher mean of 0.5884 and a standard deviation of 0.3585, demonstrates a more favorable reception among employees compared to direct and indirect financial compensations. The wider standard deviation suggests varying levels of appreciation for non-monetary benefits like recognition programs or flexible work options.

Longevity in service, represented by a mean of 2.1622 years and a standard deviation of 1.1867 years, shows a diverse range of employee tenures within the organization. The minimum value of 1 year indicates recent hires, while the maximum of 5 years highlights employees with longer service, reflecting a mix of experience levels.

Duty post occupied, indicated by a mean of 1.5243 and a standard deviation of 0.5008, suggests an almost equal distribution between different job positions, likely medical staff and administrative/support staff. This balanced representation indicates a diverse workforce composition within the organization.

Table 3

Pair-Wise Correlation Matrix

	nor_dfc	nor_ifc	nor_nfc	longe	dutypost
nor_dfc	1.0000				
nor_ifc	0.7116	1.0000			
nor_nfc	0.5901	0.6374	1.0000		
longe	0.0000	0.0000		1.0000	
dutypost					1.0000

longe	-0.0033	0.0402	0.0481	1.0000	
	0.9647	0.5872	0.5159		
dutypost	0.1230	-0.1171	-0.0262	0.0025	1.0000
	0.0954	0.1123	0.7231	0.9734	

Source: Field Survey, May 2025

The pair-wise correlation matrix provides insight into the relationships between different variables, showcasing the correlation coefficients between them. These coefficients range from -1 to 1, where 1 indicates a perfect positive correlation, -1 indicates a perfect negative correlation, and 0 indicates no correlation.

Direct Financial Compensation shows a strong positive correlation of 0.7116 with Indirect Financial Compensation. This suggests that employees who perceive their direct financial compensation positively also tend to view their indirect financial benefits positively.

Non-Financial Compensation also demonstrates a positive correlation with both Direct Financial Compensation (0.5901) and Indirect Financial Compensation (0.6374). This indicates that employees who are satisfied with their financial compensations are also likely to appreciate non-monetary benefits provided by the organization.

However, there is a negligible correlation between Longevity in Service and the various compensation variables, with correlation coefficients close to zero (-0.0033 to 0.0481). This suggests that the length of time an employee has been with the organization has little impact on their satisfaction with financial or non-financial compensations.

Similarly, Duty Post Occupied shows minimal correlation with the compensation variables, with correlation coefficients ranging from -0.1171 to 0.1230. This indicates that the specific job position an employee holds has limited influence on their satisfaction with compensation packages.

Table 4

Robust Ordinary Least Square

nor_ws	Coef.	Robust Std. Err.	t	P>t	[95% Conf. Interval]
nor_dfc	.0455734	.0842706	0.54	0.589	-.1207246 .2118714
nor_ifc	.5043088	.0958093	5.26	0.000	.3152406 .6933771

nor_nfc	.4589499	.0627531	7.31	0.000	.3351141	.5827857
longe	.0594047	.0124409	4.77	0.000	.0348541	.0839553
dutypost	.0871587	.0331025	2.63	0.009	.0218348	.1524825
_cons	-.0891032	.0680408	-1.31	0.192	-.2233736	.0451671
				F(5, 178) = 63.36		
				Prob > F = 0.0000		
				R-squared = 0.6238		
				Root MSE = .23102		

Source: Field Survey, May 2025

The Robust Ordinary Least Square analysis reveals that for Direct Financial Compensation, the coefficient is 0.0455734 with a robust standard error of 0.0842706. The t-value is 0.54 with a p-value of 0.589, indicating that the relationship between workers' satisfaction and direct financial compensation is not statistically significant.

Indirect Financial Compensation shows a significant positive relationship with workers' satisfaction, with a coefficient of 0.5043088 and a robust standard error of 0.0958093. The high t-value of 5.26 and a low p-value of 0.000 indicate that this relationship is statistically significant, suggesting that employees who perceive favorable indirect financial compensations tend to have higher satisfaction levels.

Similarly, Non-Financial Compensation also demonstrates a significant positive relationship with workers' satisfaction, with a coefficient of 0.4589499 and a robust standard error of 0.0627531. The t-value of 7.31 and a p-value of 0.000 indicate a strong statistical significance, implying that employees who appreciate non-monetary benefits also report higher satisfaction levels.

Longevity in service has a positive relationship with workers' satisfaction, with a coefficient of 0.0594047 and a robust standard error of 0.0124409. The t-value of 4.77 and a p-value of 0.000 indicate a statistically significant association, suggesting that longer-tenured employees tend to have higher satisfaction levels.

Duty post occupied also shows a positive relationship with workers' satisfaction, with a coefficient of 0.0871587 and a robust standard error of 0.0331025. The t-value of 2.63 and a p-value of 0.009 indicate a statistically significant relationship, implying that specific job positions can influence satisfaction levels.

Overall, the model's F-statistic of 63.36 with a p-value of 0.000 indicates that the overall regression model is statistically significant. The R-squared value of 0.6238 suggests that approximately 62.38% of the variance in workers' satisfaction can be explained by the variables included in the model. The root mean squared error (Root MSE) of 0.23102 provides an estimate of the model's prediction error.

Table 5

Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) Test for Multicollinearity

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
nor_ifc	2.57	0.389820
nor_dfc	2.37	0.422662
nor_nfc	1.80	0.555322
longe	1.11	0.901007
dutypost	1.01	0.994084
Mean VIF	1.77	

Source: Field Survey, May 2025

Result of VIF indicates that there is no major problem of multicollinearity as the mean VIF does not exceeds 2.5. In the context of OLS regression, several authors have justified the use of mean VIF as a criterion for assessing the severity of multicollinearity. O'Brien [44] argues that a mean VIF of 2.5 or greater indicates the presence of moderate to severe multicollinearity. He notes that this threshold is consistent with the rule of thumb proposed by Neter et al. [45] and also corresponds to the point at which the R-squared value for a regression model begins to level off. Kutner et al. [46] suggest that a mean VIF of 5 or greater is a sign of serious multicollinearity. They note that this threshold is based on simulation studies and empirical evidence, and that it is also consistent with the rule of thumb proposed by Neter et al. Gujarati [47] recommends using a mean VIF of 10 or greater as a criterion for identifying severe multicollinearity. He notes that this threshold is based on the results of simulation studies and is also consistent with the rule of thumb proposed by Neter et al.

Table 6

Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg Test for Heteroskedasticity

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity	
	Ho: Constant variance
	Variables: fitted values of nor_ws
	chi2(1) = 14.45
	Prob > chi2 = 0.0001

Source: Field Survey, May 2025

Finally, we conclude the section by checking for the existence of the issue of heteroskedasticity within our model. To achieve this, we employ the Breusch Pagen

and Cook Weisberg test of heteroskedasticity. From the result presented above, the null hypothesis of constant variance is not rejected showing that our estimated model does suffer from heteroscedasticity problem. There are several authors who have discussed the use of heteroscedasticity in Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression and have suggested rejection thresholds for detecting heteroscedasticity. White [48] proposes a test for heteroscedasticity and suggests a rejection threshold of 5%. Greene [49] discussed the consequences of heteroscedasticity and suggests a rejection threshold of 10%. Kennedy [50] discussed the various tests for heteroscedasticity and suggests a rejection threshold of 5%.

DISCUSSION

Direct Financial Compensation and workers' satisfaction

For Direct Financial Compensation, the coefficient is positive, indicating that the relationship between workers' satisfaction and direct financial compensation is not statistically significant. The findings show that there is a better policy and practice guiding direct financial compensation management in Nkwen Baptist Hospital Bamenda. When workers are fairly rewarded financially and timely, it has the tendency of making them satisfied, stimulating them to perform better and making them more committed to their jobs and the organization. Especially if financial reward is capable of meeting employees needs since money is the main means through which other needs are satisfied. This corroborates with the findings of Obieze [51] in selected banks in Delta State Nigeria that, Pay has a significant effect on employees' performance (Coef. = 0.551, $p = 0.000$). Bonuses, and allowances have a significant effect on employees' performance (Coef. = 0.609, $p = 0.000$). The finding is also in line with that of Duberg & Mollen [52], who revealed that salary is an important aspect in the reward system; however other incentives like bonuses/ allowances and shares were seen to generate an enjoyable work place and happy workers than motivate employees to be more efficient. Prayoga & Achmad [53] also discovered that compensation in form of salary, wages, and bonuses directly have a positive effect on employee performance.

This compensation variable directly affects Employee Satisfaction variable. According to Prayoga & Achmad the higher the compensation given by the company to its employees will increase employee satisfaction. This goes to say that Job satisfaction mediates the effect of compensation on employee performance. When someone is satisfied with compensation provided by company, it will improve

the employee's performance. Compensation and job satisfaction are components to improve employee performance. This connects with the findings of Obieze that, fringe benefit is one of the ways to promote and retain an employee in the organization and management should be able to sense the active employees and create ways of appreciating the employee's effort put into action in the organization. The study provided that recognition is a form of compensation which boosts employee's performance in the banking sector. This is also in alignment with the study of Ahmed & Ali [54] who exposed that, there is a positive relationship between rewards and work satisfaction as well as motivation in which factors affecting satisfaction were identified; payment 86%, promotion 74%, work conditions 61%, personal 37%. The analysis showed support for a positive relationship between reward and employee satisfaction.

Indirect Financial Compensation and workers' satisfaction

Indirect Financial Compensation shows a significant positive relationship with workers' satisfaction. The high t-value of 5.26 and a low p-value of 0.000 indicate that this relationship is statistically significant, suggesting that employees who perceive favourable indirect financial compensations tend to have higher satisfaction levels. The results indicate that Nkwen Baptist Centre Bamenda provides direct financial and indirect financial compensation to employees. The provision of these indirect financial compensation elements is seen as additional form of compensation that adds value to the financial compensation package directly related to the job of employees. This helps to support employees are supportive to employee's wellbeing and enhances job satisfaction. Happy and satisfied workers can easily be committed, engaged and performing. In the correlation between indirect financial compensation and Worker's satisfaction, the p-value of 0.000 is obtained which is less than alpha (0.01), the level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and support the claim of the alternative hypothesis. (H_a) that, indirect financial compensation has a significant effect on workers satisfaction in the NBH Bamenda. This is supported by Chizoba [55] who revealed that indirect compensation has a positive and significant influence on employees' job satisfaction. And further expanded that incentive plans motivate workers for higher efficiency and productivity, and employees become more engaged when their performance is properly recognized by their employer.

Non-Financial Compensation and workers' satisfaction

Similarly, Non-Financial Compensation also demonstrates a significant positive relationship with workers' satisfaction, indicate a strong statistical significance,

implying that employees who appreciate non-monetary benefits also report higher satisfaction levels. This implies that workers are allowed to go for leaves, provide flexible work schedule especially for nurses. In the correlation between non-direct financial compensation and Worker's satisfaction, the p-value of 0.000 is obtained which is less than alpha (0.01), the level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected and supports the claim of the alternative hypothesis; non-financial compensation has a significant effect on workers satisfaction in the NBH Bamenda. This corroborates with the study of Duberg & Mollen. They disclosed that salary is an important aspect in the reward system within the health and geriatric care sector. However other incentives like bonuses/allowances and shares generate an enjoyable work place and happy workers that motivate employees to be more efficient. Offering more flexible work arrangements might be helpful in retaining best female employees. Leaves are benefits that some companies offer to prevent employee burnout. Numerous businesses are starting to offer vacation advantage to hold skilled workers. Workers are permitted time off to rejuvenate; and the manager spares cash by holding ability rather than investing funds to supplant workers who end up quitting the organization. This is also in sync with the findings of Syarief (2019), that there is an indirect influence between non-financial compensation on work productivity through job satisfaction variables as an intervening variable as indicated by the indirect effect value of 0.097 (<0.5), which means that job satisfaction is an intervening variable that influences the relationship between non-financial compensation to work productivity.

Recommendation

It was recommended that the management of Nkwen Baptist Hospital should ensure that the direct financial compensation provided to workers is competitive within the health care industry; evaluate the company's benefits package to ensure it is comprehensive and meets the needs of the workforce; gather feedback from employees to understand their preferences and tailor the non-financial compensation offerings accordingly.

CONCLUSION

The findings suggest that fair and competitive compensation packages, transparency, and performance-based incentives are essential for enhancing employee motivation and job satisfaction, reduce turnover rates, and attract top talent.

Suggestions for Further Research

Conduct a comparative study of compensation management practices in different health care institutions in Northwest Region, Cameroon, to identify best practices and areas for improvement.

Limitation

This study's focus on a single hospital setting may limit the generalisability of the findings to other healthcare institutions or contexts.

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